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Project Progress Report for Month 10

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Executive Summary

The project *SP*Ecification, *AN*alysis & *Re-calibration of High Energy p*Article Data (**SPEARHEAD**) is a 3 year-long Research and Innovation action funded by the Horizon Europe framework programme of the European Union (EU) [<https://spearhead-he.eu>]. It has eight partners from six European countries. **SPEARHEAD** commenced on **January 1, 2024**. This document reports the progress achieved from the start of the project until the end of *October 2024*, which constitutes **Deliverable D1.3**. Progress is organized by *work package (WP)* and *task*, with each *WP* containing a *summary of advancements relative to the deliverable schedule outlined in the Description of Action (DoA)*. *Key points per WP are presented in blue text boxes*. Additionally, details regarding *publication and dissemination efforts to date*, the *project's impact*, and an *explanation of resources* are included.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	iv
1 Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress	1
1.1 Objectives	1
1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP.....	3
1.2.1 Work Package 1.....	3
1.2.2 Work Package 2.....	5
1.2.3 Work Package 3.....	10
1.2.4 Work Package 4.....	24
1.2.5 Work Package 5.....	30
1.2.6 Work Package 6.....	35
1.2.7 Work Package 7.....	37
1.2.8 Work Package 8.....	38
1.3 Impact.....	40
2 Explanation of the resources	42
3 Publications & Dissemination Activities	43
References	45
List of Acronyms/Abbreviations	46

List of Figures

FIGURE 1-1 – THE COMMON NEXTCLOUD REPOSITORY OF SPEARHEAD	4
FIGURE 1-2 – THE CURRENT MODEL OF THE ELECTRON PROTON HELIUM INSTRUMENT (EPHIN).....	6
FIGURE 1-3 – THE CURRENT DESCRIPTIONS OF SOLAR ORBITER/HET, ULYSSES/KET AND SOHO/ERNE RESULTING FROM SPEARHEAD	7
FIGURE 1-4 – THE CURRENT DESCRIPTION OF BEPICOLOMBO/SIXS RESULTING FROM SPEARHEAD.....	8
FIGURE 1-5 – PRELIMINARY RESPONSE FUNCTIONS FOR SOHO/EPHIN (A), SOHO/ERNE (B), BEPICOLOMBO/SIXS (C), AND SOHO/HET (D).....	9
FIGURE 1-6 – A COMPARISON OF TIME-SERIES OF OUR UNFOLDED PROTON FLUXES WITH THOSE OF THE SEP-EM REFERENCE DATASET	11
FIGURE 1-7 – THE FLUENCE (PANEL ON THE LEFT) AND PEAK PROTON FLUX (PANEL ON THE RIGHT) SPECTRA FOR THE EVENTS OF FIGURE 1-6.....	11

FIGURE 1-8 - COMPARISON OF THE DERIVED INTEGRAL COUNTRATES WITH ACE OBSERVABLES FOR 4 SREM CHANNELS (TOP PANELS) AND THE OBTAINED PEARSON CORRELATION COEFFICIENT FOR ALL 15 SREM CHANNELS	12
FIGURE 1-9 - HEPAD PROTON RESPONSE FUNCTIONS FOR GOES-06 (LEFT HAND SIDE) AND FOR GOES-08 (RIGHT HAND SIDE). THE RFs FOR GOES-08 ARE ALSO APPLICABLE FOR THE HEPAD UNITS ON SUCCESSIVE GOES PAYLOADS.....	13
FIGURE 1-10 - CROSS-PLOTS OF GOES06/HEPAD (LEFT HAND SIDE) AND GOES08/HEPAD (RIGHT HAND SIDE) AGAINST IMP8-GME PROTON FLUXES RE-BINNED AT THE HEPAD NOMINAL ENERGY VALUES. THE RED POINTS CORRESPOND TO THE BACKGROUND SUBTRACTED HEPAD FLUXES, THE GREEN ONES TO RESCALED ONES USING LOGARITHMIC LINEAR FIT AND THE BLUE ONES RESCALED USING LINEAR FIT COEFFICIENTS.	14
FIGURE 1-11 - CROSS-PLOTS OF GOES06/HEPAD (LEFT HAND SIDE) AND GOES08/HEPAD (RIGHT HAND SIDE) COUNT-RATES AGAINST IMP8 GME EXPECTED COUNT-RATES. THE RED POINTS CORRESPOND TO THE BACKGROUND SUBTRACTED HEPAD MEASUREMENTS, THE GREEN ONES TO RESCALED ONES USING LOGARITHMIC LINEAR FIT AND THE BLUE ONES RESCALED USING LINEAR FIT COEFFICIENTS.	15
FIGURE 1-12 - AVERAGED (LEFT HAND SIDE) AND MAXIMUM DIFFERENTIAL PROTON FLUX SPECTRA (RIGHT HAND SIDE) DURING SELECTED SPEs.	18
FIGURE 1-13 - RIGIDITY SPECTRA DURING SELECTED STAGES OF SUB-GLE EVENT ON 7 MARCH 2012, COMPARED WITH PREVIOUS RECONSTRUCTION AND WEAK GLE-CAUSING SPECTRUM DURING THE LATE PHASE OF GLE 71.....	19
FIGURE 1-14 - HELIUM SPECTRUM AT ENERGIES BETWEEN ABOUT 60 MEV/AMU AND 250 MEV/AMU	20
FIGURE 1-15 - TYPICAL ENERGY LOSS DISTRIBUTIONS (PANEL ON THE LEFT) AND THE RATIO OF THE DISTRIBUTIONS (PANEL ON THE RIGHT).....	20
FIGURE 1-16 - A RHESSI PHOTON SPECTRUM THAT IS USED AS INPUT (PANEL ON THE LEFT HAND SIDE) AND THE RESULTING COUNTING RATE AS A FUNCTION OF ENERGY THRESHOLD (PANEL ON THE RIGHT HAND SIDE)	21
FIGURE 1-17 - EVOLUTION OF M AS A FUNCTION OF ENERGY FOR 5 SEP EVENTS AND THEIR MEAN CASE	22
FIGURE 1-18 - THE RESPONSE FUNCTIONS OF SSD F TO PROTONS AND HELIUM.....	23
FIGURE 1-19 - LIST OF EVENTS THAT ARE CONSIDERED OF HIGHEST PRIORITY FOR THE FIRST CASE STUDIES OF THE PROJECT.....	25
FIGURE 1-20 - SUBSET LIST OF INTENSE SEPs MEASURED BY ERNE AND THEIR ESTIMATED SOLAR SOURCES (X-RAY FLARE, CMEs).....	25
FIGURE 1-21 - SOLAR ORBITER STIX DETECTION (LEFT: IMAGE, RIGHT: LIGHT CURVES) OF THE FAR-SIDE FLARE ASSOCIATED WITH THE ERNE SEP EVENT 171.....	26
FIGURE 1-22 - THREE-DIMENSIONAL FIT OF THE SHOCK WAVE ASSOCIATED WITH THE RECENT 11TH OF MAY 2024 CME.....	27

FIGURE 1-23 - DISTRIBUTION OF THE ALFVÉN MACH NUMBER AT THE SURFACE OF THE MODELLED SHOCK WAVE FOR THE 11TH OF MAY 2024 CME EVENT AND MAGNETIC FIELD LINES CONNECTED TO DIFFERENT SPACECRAFT..... 28

FIGURE 1-24 - EVOLUTION OF THE SHOCK PARAMETERS (SHOCK SPEED, ALFVÉN MACH, FAST-MODE MACH, DE-HOFFMAN TELLER SHOCK SPEED, UPSTREAM ALFVÉN SPEED) MODELLED ALONG MAGNETIC FIELD LINES CONNECTED TO EARTH DURING THE 11TH OF MAY 2024 (GLE74). 28

FIGURE 1-25 - PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF INTERPLANETARY CONDITIONS FOR THE 2024-06-11 STRONG SEP EVENT WITH THE ORBITAL CONFIGURATION (TOP LEFT), THE IN SITU SIGNATURE OF THE ICME AT PARKER SOLAR PROBE (TOP LEFT), THE CME OBSERVED BY LASCO (BOTTOM LEFT) AND THE SEP MEASURED BY GOES (BOTTOM RIGHT) 29

FIGURE 1-26 - THE ONSET TIME DETERMINATION OF THE SEP EVENT ON 17-05-2001 FROM SOHO/ERNE >100 MEV IONS COUNTING RATE..... 30

FIGURE 1-27 - SIMILAR TO FIGURE 1-26 BUT FOR THE ELECTRONS OF ~ 5 MEV DURING THE SEP EVENT ON 09-05-1998 FROM ULYSSES/KET FLUX 31

FIGURE 1-28 - A JOVIAN ELECTRON EVENT (PANEL ON THE LEFT) AND AN SEP EVENT (PANEL ON THE RIGHT) OBSERVED BY ULYSSES/KET 31

FIGURE 1-29 - THE ULYSSES TRAJECTORY (RADIAL DISTANCE AND LATITUDE - TOP PANEL) FOR THE WHOLE MISSION AND THE IDENTIFIED SEE EVENTS ON THE BACKGROUND OF ULYSSES ORBIT (BOTTOM PANEL)..... 32

FIGURE 1-30 - SPECTRA OF THE INTENSITY J(R) FOR DIFFERENT PERIODS OF THE SUB-GLE EVENT (LEFT PANEL) AND FLUENCE (TIME- AND ENERGY INTEGRATED), RIGHT PANEL) F(> E) ON 09 JUNE 1968. THE TIME INTERVALS IN THE LEFT PANEL ARE GIVEN IN UT. THE GREY LINE AND SHADED AREA INDICATE THE GCR BACKGROUND WITH THE HELIOSPHERIC MODULATION Φ OF 752 MV IN JUNE 1968. 33

FIGURE 1-31 - A SCREENSHOT OF THE GUI 33

FIGURE 1-32 - COMPOSITE FIGURE WITH THE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS ALREADY IMPLEMENTED AND IN USE BY SPEARHEAD 39

FIGURE 1-33 - THE IDENTIFIED KEY TARGET GROUPS FOR SPEARHEAD 40

FIGURE 3-1 - COMPOSITE FIGURE WITH INSTANCES OF THE PROJECT'S FIRST WORKSHOP 43

FIGURE 3-2 - COMPOSITE FIGURE WITH INSTANCES OF THE PROJECT'S DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES 44

List of Tables

TABLE 1-1: WP1 DELIVERABLES..... 3

TABLE 1-2: WP2 DELIVERABLES..... 5

TABLE 1-3: WP3 DELIVERABLES..... 10

TABLE 1-4: THE DERIVED SCALING FACTORS FOR GOES06 AND GOES08 HEPAD FLUXES 16

TABLE 1-5: THE VALUES OF $G \Delta E [CM^2 SR MEV]$ 22

TABLE 1-6: WP4 DELIVERABLES 24

TABLE 1-7: WP5 DELIVERABLES 30

TABLE 1-8: WP6 DELIVERABLES 35

TABLE 1-9: WP7 DELIVERABLES 37

TABLE 1-10: WP8 DELIVERABLES 38

1 Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and Overview of the progress

SPEARHEAD focuses on high energy particles, originating either from the Sun (i.e., Solar Energetic Particles – *SEPs*) or our Galaxy (Galactic Cosmic Rays – *GCRs*). The project will address several open scientific questions on the acceleration, release and propagation physical processes of such particles. In doing so, **SPEARHEAD** provides novel high-level data products based on recalibrations of radiation monitor data -- on so-far unreleased data from science-grade instruments, and measurements of ground-based neutron monitors; technical notes on the response functions of several science-grade and monitoring instruments, utilising GEANT4 modelling; comprehensive catalogues of near-relativistic ions and relativistic electrons in strong SEP (and/or Ground Level Enhancement - *GLE*) events as well as Forbush decreases - *FD* events of *GCRs* from a fleet of different instruments onboard spacecraft, at radial distances from 0.04 to 5 AU; scientific and data analysis as well as tools enabling the coordinated analysis of high energy particle data with contexts observations.

1.1 Objectives

SPEARHEAD performs a comprehensive study of high energy particle observations in the heliosphere (>100 MeV/nucleon ions and >1 MeV electrons). While observations of deka-MeV protons are readily available from several instruments onboard various spacecraft in several positions throughout the heliosphere, hecto-MeV protons are not routinely observed with most science-grade instruments aboard the heliospheric fleet. However, several instruments can register these particles by utilising methods other than the standard ΔE -E method, e.g., ΔE - ΔE [Kühl *et al.*, 2017] and ΔE -Cherenkov [Marquardt & Heber, 2019], which can significantly extend the energy range of the instrument. In addition, radiation monitoring instruments carried by several heliospheric missions can also provide broad energy channels at high energies, which are very useful if a successful cross-calibration can be achieved with science-grade instruments to physical flux units at well-defined energies. Such analyses and methods to extend energetic particle observations to the high energy range in multiple locations in the heliosphere are being carried out and developed within **SPEARHEAD**. *As a result, we will deliver, validate, and distribute new high-level data of high energy particle intensities for the community through our own servers as well as through ESA and NASA archives and platforms (ESA/Datalabs) to the whole heliophysics and space weather research communities.*

In addition to developing tools and data products for high-energy particles, the team analyses energetic particle events and their relations to solar parameters such as X-ray flare peak flux and location, magnetic connectivity to the eruption site, parameters of the coronal mass ejection (CME) and the waves driven by them in regions magnetically connected to the observing spacecraft, etc.

The *scientific objective* of **SPEARHEAD** is to **provide answers to the following science questions:**

SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions, beyond 100 MeV/n and 1 MeV, respectively?

SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release from acceleration sites in the solar corona?

SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?

Related to the science questions, the **main technical objectives of SPEARHEAD** are:

TO1: to develop and distribute analysis tools to extract high-energy particle fluxes from particle detectors designed to operate at lower energies or to yield monitoring data. Response functions of spacecraft instruments will be determined and particle fluxes of the very high energy particles as a function of time and energy will be delivered.

TO2: to process and cross-calibrate a large number of data to produce high-energy particle flux datasets and distribute them to the community.

TO3: to validate the data against intermittent direct spectrometer observations.

SPEARHEAD will open all its results and facilitate the future use of the developed value-added data products, methods and analysis tools by integrating them into existing infrastructures like SEPServer (utu.sepsserver.eu), NMDB (<https://nmdb.eu>), the International GLE database (<https://gle.oulu.fi>), the French National Data Center (CDPP; <https://cdpp-archive.cnes.fr/>) and the large-scale open access infrastructure ESA/Datalabs (<https://datalabs.esa.int/>). The novel datasets will also be directly fed to the data archives of Space Agencies (ESA and NASA). This ensures the maximal science return from the project. **SPEARHEAD** will also facilitate the use of its results for radiation environment analyses, which represent a major issue for all present and future space science and human exploration missions. Moreover, the dedicated, well-targeted User Engagement part of **SPEARHEAD** will provide a direct link of the project's outputs to the needs of the planned and/or under-design missions of nowadays.

Summary of the Reporting Period

In the first 10 months of **SPEARHEAD**, activities evolved as planned, with a primary emphasis on the recruitment of personnel and the completion of the *Preparatory phase* of the project. This phase laid the foundation for the subsequent implementation of key strategic plans, including the Data Management Plan (**D1.2**), the Tools and Data Development Plan (**D6.1**) and the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (**D8.2**). Additionally, during this phase the rapid implementation of the Communication infrastructure (**D1.1**) allowed the un-obstructed internal collaboration among the Partners of the project and the establishment of **SPEARHEAD's** web portal (**D8.1**) provided a direct communication channel with the external users and the targeted user communities of **SPEARHEAD**. The completion of the *Preparatory Phase* was signalled by the successful completion of *Milestone 1 (MS1)* of the project. Focus was put on the *Data and Analysis methods*, with **WP2** and **WP3** putting effort on setting up and running instrument simulations and cross-calibrations paving the way for **D2.1** and **D3.1** that will be submitted at the end of the year. Additionally, **WP4** centred on the selection of representative case studies for CMEs, whose analysis is geared towards answering the **SQs** of **SPEARHEAD** (**D4.1**) and began the commencement of **D4.2** which is focused on the context observations for the selected case studies, scheduled for the end of this year. Once the *Main Phase* of the project was initiated, the new data sets from **WP2** were used for the establishment of novel catalogues of high energy SEP events for both protons and electrons. The output of these scanings underpin the upcoming deliverables **D5.1** and **D5.2** at the end of this year and month 18, respectively. Finally, the Github repository of **SPEARHEAD** was implemented and will be populated with initial versions of tools by the end of the year (**D6.2**).

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP

1.2.1 Work Package 1

Work Package 1 (WP1) ensures the efficient management and monitoring of the consortium and the project. It further provides the project with efficient management and communication Information Technology (IT) solutions. *Table 1-1* below summarizes the **Deliverables of WP1**.

Table 1-1: WP1 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D1.1	Communication infrastructure	Intranet and mailing list services for the consortium established	NOA	2
D1.2	Data management plan	Data management plan of the SPEARHEAD project	NOA	6
D1.3	Project Progress Report for Month 10	Progress Report for Interim Review	NOA	10
D1.4	Project Progress Report for Month 27	Progress Report for Interim Review	NOA	27

Task 1-1. Legal and contractual management (NOA)

The Work for this Task was performed after the selection of the project, prior to the start of the recent activities. It involved the drafting of the *Consortium Agreement (CA)*, the implementation of the *Description of Actions (DoA)*, the initiation of the collaboration with the *Project Officer (PO)* and the update of the projects' profile information in the *European Union (EU)* portal. It led to the successful *signing of the CA*, the *signing of the Grant Agreement (GA)* and the *initiation of the project's research activities on 01/01/2024*.

Task 1.2 Management and reporting (NOA, partners: all)

Within SPEARHEAD work was initially focused on the implementation of a management structure, which encompasses: the *Project Management Board (PMB)*, the *Consortium Board (CB)* and the *External Advisory Board (EAC)*. **PMB** comprises of the *WP leaders* and the *Principal Investigator (PI)* and their basic duty is to follow the progress of the project on a WP level. The **CB** is the highest decision-making body and is responsible for proper administration of the project. The **EAC** was established early on in the project; it follows the project and provides assistance and consultancy upon request and/or need that may emerge. Detail information on the management structure is included in **D1.1**

Within Task 1.2 activities, the first version of the project's *Data Management Plan (DMP)* has been designed and documented in deliverable **D1.2**. The **DMP** outlines how data will be managed throughout the project, with a focus on adhering to *FAIR* principles (*Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability*) and open science practices. It covers how data will be collected, processed, and shared, including formats, storage locations, and accessibility mechanisms. Data products, including calibrated high energy particle datasets and **SPEARHEAD** catalogues on SEPs, ICMEs and Forbush decreases, will be stored in *Zenodo*, where a dedicated community has been established for the project (<https://zenodo.org/communities/spearhead/>), and integrated, where possible, into open access repositories such as the AMDA database, SEPserver, ESA and NASA

archives. The project ensures interoperability by following international data standards and using common formats like CDF and NetCDF, as well as data/metadata protocols and naming conventions introduced by the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC) and the SERPENTINE project. To promote reusability, datasets will be openly licensed, and tools for data analysis will be shared on platforms such as *GitHub* (see also deliverable **D6.1 – Tools and data development plan**). Long-term data preservation will be achieved through trusted repositories, with open access to scientific publications where possible. The **DMP**, including detailed descriptions of all data assets anticipated by the project, has been implemented and will be maintained in the *Argos* platform (<https://argos.openaire.eu/home>). The **DMP** will be continuously updated throughout the project, reflecting the progress made in the provision of calibrated high-quality datasets and novel catalogues generated by the project to the scientific community.

Task 1.3 Communication infrastructure (NOA)

In order to facilitate the internal communications of SPEARHEAD, NOA implemented an *internal cloud solution* (available at: <https://files.nextcloud-he.eu>) which has been used as an internal file repository (see *Figure 1-1*) since the start of the project.

Figure 1-1 – The common Nextcloud repository of SPEARHEAD

Moreover, mailing lists have been implemented to facilitate communication among the partners of the project (e.g. spearhead.all@noa.gr), the participants of each WP (e.g. spearhead.wp1@noa.gr) and to ensure flawless transmission of decisions and information through the interconnected bodies of the management structure (see previous task). Additionally, scientific and technical work are assisted via the implementation of a Mattermost channel (<https://team.spearhead-he.eu/>) that offers direct chats/discussions. Finally, a *Google Drive* was set up to allow access to scientists outside the consortium.

Task 1.4 Reporting and Administration of the Community financial contribution (NOA, partners:all)

Reporting tasks for the project have been initiated and further facilitated through the management structure. The Interim Report at hand is an output of such reporting at work. Financial statements are not provided at this point but will be available in a few months through the Periodic Report.

During this first reporting period WP1 submitted the assigned Deliverables (D1.1 and D1.2; Table 1-1) on time, as per the DoA and the GA. For the Interim Periodic Review, the report at hand was compiled and submitted, constituting D1.3 as per Table 1-1.

1.2.2 Work Package 2

Particle measurements in interplanetary space as well as in the atmosphere of a planet (Earth and Mars) depend on the local environment in which the data are taken. In order to derive physical quantities, the response function within this environment needs to be computed by means of e.g. Geant4 models that include the instrument setup as well as the ambient environment. That is the focus of **Work Package 2 (WP2)**, the deliverables of which are described in the *Table 1-2* below.

Table 1-2: WP2 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D2.1	Geant4 models, part I	Report and delivery of the Geant4 models of SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN, Chandra/EPHIN, Solar Orbiter/ HET and BepiColombo/SIXS	CAU	12
D2.2	Updated NM yield function	Report on the updated NM yield function	UOULU	16
D2.3	Simulated response functions, part I	Report and delivery of input and analysis programs to compute response functions using Geant4	CAU	18
D2.4	Geant4 models, part II	Report and delivery of the Geant4 model of the Ulysses/KET	CAU	18
D2.5	Simulated response functions, part II	Delivery of the validated response function for Ulysses KET	CAU	24

Task 2-1. Construction of (updated) Geant4 models (CAU, UTU)

The main work in WP2 has progressed as planned directed to Task 2-1 (**D2.1** and **D2.3**) and Task 2.3 (**D2.2**) led by *CAU* and *UOULU*. In particular, Task 2.1 focuses on the creation of the **SPEARHEAD GEANT4** and *Python* tools to compute the **particle response functions**. A first draft of the delivery report on the *GEANT4* instrument description files together with a detailed manual to set up the corresponding programs exists. The tools are realized utilizing the most recent virtual machine provided by the GEANT4 community via <https://extra.lip2ib.in2p3.fr/G4/>. This virtual machine, obtained from the corresponding [download page](#), contains all GEANT4 modules needed to implement the instrument GDML description files.

A University of Kiel *Gitlab* page has been set up that includes the code as well as the instruction to set up the GEANT4 machine and tools developed. A screenshot of the machine is shown below in *Figure 1-2* which presents the current model of the *Electron Proton Helium INSTRUMENT (EPHIN)* including a compact mass model of the SOHO spacecraft. In addition, the screenshot shows the track of a 5 MeV electron producing secondary particles.

CAU will utilize the virtual machine in a lecture about measurement methods in extraterrestrial physics. This serves as a test situation for potential users. *GDML models have been implemented for the other instruments shown in the following figures*.

Progress has been achieved with respect to Solar Orbiter High Energy Telescope (HET): The first figure displays on the left and right panel a GDML drawing of HET aboard Solar Orbiter positioned with respect to the newly implemented mass model of the spacecraft and a close-up of the instrument and its housing, respectively (see *Figure 1-3*; top panels).

The middle panels in *Figure 1-3* show the same for the High Energy Detector (HED) and the Kiel Electron Telescope (KET). Thus, the task “*The existing Geant3 models for the KET aboard Ulysses will be updated from Geant3 to Geant4, including advanced modelling of the Cherenkov shower calorimeter*” has been achieved and validation utilizing calibration runs is worked upon.

Figure 1-2 – The current model of the Electron Proton Helium INstrument (EPHIN)

GEANT4 model of HET with electronic box and sc-shielding

GDML GEANT4 model of the HET

Ulysses Kiel Electron Telescope (KET) sketch used for the definition of the GDML file shown on the right.

GDML model of the KET

CAD model of the SOHO/ERNE

The GDML model of SOHO/ERNE consists of 300 elements.

Figure 1-3 – The current descriptions of Solar Orbiter/HET, Ulysses/KET and SOHO/ERNE resulting from SPEARHEAD

Concerning “SOHO / ERNE Geant4 model will be modernised based on a newly generated CAD model of the instrument generated from the drawings. A spacecraft model will also be included.” progress has been achieved. The model of the instrument exists in GDML. The model includes the high-energy HED (see bottom panels of *Figure 1-3*) and the low-energy LED heads (not shown here), the instrument electronics, and a shield representing the spacecraft. The shield material composition and density may be adjusted. The model underwent full-sky simulations in *GEANT4* for protons between 100 MeV and 10 GeV, allowing an expansion of the energy range.

Concerning the SIXS aboard the BepiColombo, progress has been made. In addition to response functions, effective energies for the particle channels were calculated. The graphical representation of the GDML model of SIXS-P is shown in the left panel of *Figure 1-4*. The model will be further improved to include the complete equivalent of the spacecraft to assess, e.g., electron scattering from the multilayer thermal shield obstructing the field of view of one of the viewing cones of SIXS-P in the cruise configuration.

We analyzed the contamination caused by protons and electrons in respective contaminated channels (e.g., cosmic ray protons in electron channels). The right panel of *Figure 1-4* below shows the cross-species response in the electron channels of SIXS-P.

Figure 1-4 – The current description of BepiColombo/SIXS resulting from SPEARHEAD

In order to compute the response functions of the SOHO EPHIN (for D2.3), the GDML was modified to describe the calibration of the instrument with ions at the Hahn-Meitner Institut Berlin. This will be documented in D2.1. Progress has been achieved for: “The *Geant4* model of EPHIN aboard SOHO will be adapted to the instrument aboard Chandra and more reliable spacecraft models will be included.”

Task 2-2. Computation of instrument response functions (CAU, UTU)

Work has mainly been carried out in preparing the task. Preliminary response functions were computed for EPHIN, HED and SIXS, as shown in *Figure 1-5*.

Energy response function for protons that penetrate SOHO/EPHIN isotropically from the front. For details see text.

Geometric factor for SOHO/ERNE/HED for protons fulfilling conditions explained in the text.

Geometric factor for SIXS for protons fulfilling conditions explained in the text.

Energy response functions for SoLo HET proton channels. For details see text.

Figure 1-5 – Preliminary response functions for SOHO/EPHIN (a), SOHO/ERNE (b), BepiColombo/SIXS (c), and SoLo/HET (d)

For SOHO/EPHIN and Chandra/EPHIN we are currently working on the energy response for backward penetrating particles that are important for interpreting single detector count rates too.

SOHO/EPHIN helium measurement capabilities were analysed here too and discussed in WP3.

Task 2-3. Update of the response function of NM to low-energy particles (UOULU)

The new generation of standard NM-64 yield functions is computed, specifically in the energy range of interest for registration of SEPs. This includes the possibility to account oblique events, namely with various incidence vertical to up to 45 degrees inclination, with a step of 15 degrees. The yield functions are also computed at various altitudes, so that each station can be modelled with his own yield function. The validation of the computations is in progress. In addition, computation of yield functions for mini-NM, would be performed, in order to model properly the response of the latter. This activity is in progress.

During the first reporting period, **all tasks within WP2 have made substantial progress**. The primary focus was on the **implementation of Geant4 models for all instruments**, laying the groundwork for the forthcoming deliverables **D2.1 and D2.4 (Table 1-2)**. Additionally, significant efforts were made towards **the computation of response functions**, which aligns with the requirements for deliverables **D2.3 and D2.5**. Furthermore, **the update of the neutron monitor response function**, in preparation for **D2.2**, advanced successfully during this period.

1.2.3 Work Package 3

Cross-calibration and re-calibration of high energy particle datasets is the focus of **Work Package 3 (WP3)**, the deliverables of which are described in the *Table 1-3* below

Table 1-3: WP3 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D3.1	Cross-calibration of SOHO / EPHIN with spectrometer data	Report on the cross-calibration of SOHO / EPHIN with AMS-02 and PAMELA	CAU	12
D3.2	Single detector counter crosscalibration	Report on the single detector counter cross- calibration for SOHO/EPHIN and Solar Orbiter/HET	CAU	14
D3.3	Recalibration of the photon sensitivity of the SOHO/EPHIN and BepiColombo/SIXS	Report on the recalibration of the photon sensitivity of the SOHO/EPHIN and BepiColombo/SIXS	CAU	18
D3.4	Cross-calibration of NMs with spacecraft instruments	Report on the cross-calibration between ground-based NMs and space-borne detectors	UOULU	18
D3.5	Cross-calibration of SOHO/ERNE with SOHO/EPHIN	Cross-calibration of SOHO / ERNE with SOHO / EPHIN	UTU	18
D3.6	Re-calibrated SREM flux datasets	Report and delivery of re-calibrated SREM flux datasets	SPARC	30
D3.7	Cross-calibrated NOAA GOES HEPAD proton flux datasets	Report and delivery of cross-calibrated NOAA GOES HEPAD proton flux datasets	SPARC	30

Task 3-1 Reanalysis/recalibration of SREM proton measurements from SREM units (SPARC)

During this task the measurements from the SREM units on board the INTEGRAL, PLANCK and HERSCHEL missions were retrieved and investigated in order to perform a reanalysis with the objective of deriving solar proton fluxes with increased quality and extended energy range. In this phase we have focused on the SREM datasets from the PLANCK and HERSCHEL missions as they do not present some of the challenges that INTEGRAL does. PLANCK and HERSCHEL were two concurrent missions orbiting the Sun-Earth Lagrange-2 point and both had a duration of approximately 4 years 2009-2013. These datasets are ideal for benchmarking the derivation of solar proton measurements as the radiation environment in L2 is dominated by SEPs with no trapped electron radiation to which SREM is also sensitive. We used the SEP reference event list (REL) to isolate periods during the PLANCK(HERSCHEL) missions that SEP events occurred and verified that the enhancements were also measured by the SREM units. For these events we adapted and applied

the SPARC-developed GENCORUM methodology to the SREM measurements and derived solar proton flux spectra from ~10 MeV up to ~1 GeV. The proton fluxes have the same cadence as the SREM measurements of 53 seconds and were derived in 100 logarithmically spaced energy bins, twice the energy resolution of the available to us SREM proton response functions. *Figure 1-6* shows a comparison of time-series of our unfolded proton fluxes with those of the SEPEM Reference Dataset (RDS) version 3.2 for the most intense SEP event that occurred during the PLANCK and HERSCHEL missions. The SREM (PLANCK) unfolded fluxes (colored) are temporally binned to the timestamps of the SEPEM RDS fluxes (black) and interpolated at the same energies for direct comparison.

Figure 1-6 – A comparison of time-series of our unfolded proton fluxes with those of the SEPEM Reference Dataset

From the proton fluxes we also calculate two of the most important macro-characteristics of SEPs, the *Fluence* (time-integrated flux) spectrum and the *Peak flux* spectrum. *Figure 1-7* shows the comparison with RDS data for the previously shown event and the insets show the ratios between the spectra from our unfolded fluxes and those of RDS.

Figure 1-7 – The fluence (panel on the left) and peak proton flux (panel on the right) spectra for the events of Figure 1-6

These results are very promising and show that high quality proton fluxes with extended energy range can be derived from SREM data. Additionally, we have investigated the effect of GCRs on SREM measurements during periods that no SEP events occurred. GCRs can be of importance for our task as their lower energies overlap with the energy ranges of solar protons and particularly for energies higher than a few hundred MeVs they could affect the proton flux derivation if they are not taken into account. We used the established engineering model of [Matthiä et al. \(2013\)](#) which uses ACE (Advanced Composition Explorer) data to estimate proton but also heavier ion fluxes every 27 days. We folded the fluxes from the model with SREM response functions that extend to 100 GeV, provided to SPARC by ESA, to derive the countrates that SREM would measure with the model fluxes as input. We then compare these model-countrates with actual measurements from INTEGRAL taking care to exclude data from all *Radiation Belt passes* and *SEP events*. Figure 1-8 below shows this comparison for 4 of the 15 of SREM channels as well as the Pearson correlation of the model countrates and the 27-day average of SREM countrates. As seen the model agrees very well with SREM countrates which clearly follow the solar modulation of GCRs and the correlation coefficients quantify this agreement with very high values of more than 0.976 at all channels. This showcases that SREM does measure GCRs and they should be taken into account for highly accurate proton flux unfolding during SEPs. We note that for particularly intense SEPs, driven and accompanied by ICMEs, the FDs that can occur makes the consideration of GCRs less crucial. However, even in such cases the duration and intensity of a FD can vary and with it the GCR contribution in SREM measurements. We are in the process of adapting our unfolding process to take into account the GCR contribution and then validate our results.

Figure 1-8 – Comparison of the derived INTEGRAL countrates with ACE observables for 4 SREM channels (top panels) and the obtained Pearson correlation coefficient for all 15 SREM channels

Task 3-2 Cross-calibration of NOAA GOES HEPAD data with IMP-8/GME (SPARC)

HEPAD datasets from the NOAA GOES missions have been retrieved in order to evaluate and cross-calibrate the measurements of high energy proton fluxes attributed to solar proton events. In addition, the response functions of HEPAD channels were used (source: [Juan Rodriguez, NOAA](#)) in order to analyze the coherence between HEPAD measurements and response functions against the selected reference dataset.

Figure 1-9 – HEPAD proton response functions for GOES-06 (left hand side) and for GOES-08 (right hand side). The RFs for GOES-08 are also applicable for the HEPAD units on successive GOES payloads

As a reference dataset, the cleaned measurements of NASA IMP8/ Goddard Medium Energy (GME) were selected [[McGuire, R. E. \(1999\)](#)]. To evaluate and calibrate the HEPAD measurements, comparisons were made against the theoretically expected values for the proton radiation environment during a series of GLEs as defined by the reference measurements of IMP8/GME.

In order to perform the comparisons we:

- resampled the 5-min HEPAD measurements in order to derive a dataset with a 30-min integration time period, i.e. equal to that of IMP8/GME
- derived and subtract the (enhanced) background level of HEPAD measurements
- extend the energy range of the IMP-8/GME proton flux to the energy range of HEPAD.

The comparisons were performed on the basis of:

- differential proton flux measurements, where the IMP-8 GME proton fluxes were extrapolated to the nominal proton energy values of HEPAD datasets by performing analytic fitting of the proton flux spectra using only the last three flux energy bins of IMP8 which correspond to proton energies of 202, 274 and 398 MeV.
- count-rate measurements, where the HEPAD count-rates were compared against the theoretically expected values for the proton radiation environment defined by the reference measurements of IMP8 GME. The expected count-rate measurements were obtained by convolving the energy-extended IMP8 flux spectra with the HEPAD proton response functions.

Based on the flux comparisons, we derived factors to rescale the HEPAD fluxes values (and/or their logarithmic values) in order to optimize their agreement with the reference fluxes. The factors were derived by performing a linear fit between the actual and the logarithmic values of the flux values. In what follows we present cross-plots of GOES06 and GOES08 HEPAD fluxes against IMP8-GME proton fluxes re-binned at the HEPAD nominal energy values before and after the application of the calibration factors (*Figure 1-10*).

Figure 1-10 – Cross-plots of GOES06/HEPAD (left hand side) and GOES08/HEPAD (right hand side) against IMP8-GME proton fluxes re-binned at the HEPAD nominal energy values. The red points correspond to the background subtracted HEPAD fluxes, the green ones to rescaled ones using logarithmic linear fit and the blue ones rescaled using linear fit coefficients.

Figure 1-11 – Cross-plots of GOES06/HEPAD (left hand side) and GOES08/HEPAD (right hand side) **count-rates** against IMP8 GME expected count-rates. The red points correspond to the background subtracted HEPAD measurements, the green ones to rescaled ones using logarithmic linear fit and the blue ones rescaled using linear fit coefficients.

The derived scaling factors - applicable for the logarithmic values of GOES06 and GOES08 HEPAD fluxes - are summarized in *Table 1-4*:

Table 1-4: The derived scaling factors for GOES06 and GOES08 HEPAD fluxes

GOES06/HEPAD	P8 - 405 MeV	P9 - 473 MeV	P10 - 622 MeV
$Flux_{cal}=Flux^{(1/a)}$	a=0.858	a=0.923	a=0.943
$Flux_{cal}=Flux/b$	b=3.21	b=1.83	b=1.22

GOES08/HEPAD	P8 - 406 MeV	P9 - 457 MeV	P10 - 583 MeV
$Flux_{cal}=Flux^{(1/a)}$	a=0.867	a=0.905	a=0.917
$Flux_{cal}=Flux/b$	b=2.47	b=1.83	b=1.59

The validity of this approach can be tested by implementing energy flux spectra comparisons for a series of available SEPs between the (relatively low energy) GOES/EPS proton flux spectra and the GOES/HEPAD flux spectra before and after applying the cross-calibrations. In what follows, we present a series of SEP spectra with focus on the comparisons between the mean and the maximum proton flux spectra (Figure 1-12). This allows us to evaluate, beyond the re-scaling of the HEPAD spectra, the impact of the background in the HEPAD measurements.

Figure 1-12 – Averaged (left hand side) and maximum differential proton flux spectra (right hand side) during selected SPEs.

Conclusions: By utilizing HEPAD response functions, we concluded that the differences between HEPAD and IMP-8/GME measurements were not attributed to the inverse methods used for the flux calculations but mainly to the actual measurements and the response functions of HEPAD. The scaling factors - derived by using IMP-8/GME - drastically improve the spectra shape as compared to the GOES/EPS measurements as long as the background is subtracted. These studies will continue in order to further refine the derivation of the scaling factors and to improve the quality of the resulting HEPAD flux series. Emphasis will be given on the derivation and the subtraction of the HEPAD background levels in order to further improve the spectra shape of GOES SEP measurements.

Task 3-3. Cross-calibration between ground-based and space-borne dataset (UOULU)

This task involves analysis of several GLEs and sub-GLEs, well measured by ground and space-borne detectors. For this purpose, several events are selected for cross-checking and inter-calibration with space probe measurements, specifically the notable event on 7 March 2012, which was measured by GOES and AMSO2, the GLE 71 event on 12 May 2012, and several other recent events such as GLE 72-74.

The aim is to derive the spectral and angular characteristics of the selected events and compare the derived spectra with the direct space-borne measurements. The task started at Month 6 with neutron monitor (NM) records preparation of validation of existing datasets. The spectra of the several selected events using NM records have been obtained and the comparison with GOES measurements is in progress.

Figure 1-13 – Rigidity spectra during selected stages of sub-GLE event on 7 March 2012, compared with previous reconstruction and weak GLE-causing spectrum during the late phase of GLE 71.

In *Figure 1-13* are presented newly derived spectra during a sub relativistic event, namely sub-GLE the notable event on 7 March 2021, which was reanalyzed using the new NM yield function (YF). Here the accuracy of the spectra is improved as well as the interval and time resolution. Comparison with GOES measurements is ongoing. New sub-GLEs are identified, the analysis of the June 2024 event is in progress.

Task 3-4. The use of low-orbiting spectrometers AMS-02 and PAMELA to calibrate and validate space-borne measurements (lead: CAU, UOULU, UTU)

Utilizing the most recent GEANT4 model of the EPHIN aboard SOHO the response function of protons and helium penetrating the instrument in all directions (4π) with an isotropic distribution has been computed. From 1996 to 2017, when detector D is working, forward penetrating particles could be separated from backward ones up to 110 MeV/amu. Between 110 MeV/amu to 250 MeV/amu backward penetrating helium at higher energies contribute to the flux. Above 250 MeV/amu helium cannot be separated from protons.

Utilizing the computed response function, we obtain a helium spectrum at energies between about 60 MeV/amu and 250 MeV/amu as indicated by the blue symbols in *Figure 1-14*. The red symbols were taken from PAMELA observations in 2006. From the figure we conclude that EPHIN and PAMELA give the same helium fluxes although the uncertainties are large above 130 MeV/amu due to the contribution of backward penetrating particles. The corresponding helium energy spectrum is shown in *Figure 1-14* and shows a good agreement with observations of PAMELA during the same period. Details will be reported in the deliverable **D3.1**.

Figure 1-14 – Helium spectrum at energies between about 60 MeV/amu and 250 MeV/amu

Proton spectra have been analyzed by [Kühl et al. \(2015, 2016\)](#) and compared to different instrumentations. In this analysis they used detector D that became noisy and was logically switched off at the end of 2017. Here we utilized detector B and show in deliverable **D3.1** that the results are in good agreement with each other taking into account the systematic errors of the methods used. The left panel of [Figure 1-15](#) displays typical energy loss distributions. The black and red curve are the energy loss distribution obtained by [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) and our proxy utilizing detector B, respectively. The right panel displays the ratio of the distribution that varies between 0.9 and 1.2, respectively. Thus, the error introduced by our proxy is within the systematic error determined by [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#).

Figure 1-15 – Typical energy loss distributions (panel on the left) and the ratio of the distributions (panel on the right)

Task 3-5. Cross-calibration between Integral single detector counters and differential particle flux dataset (SPARC, CAU)

For this Task, work has been performed within WP2. Preliminary response functions for SOHO/EPHIN are shown in [Figure 1-18](#). A Python tool to convolute the response function with an appropriate *Force Field Model* is under development.

Task 3-6. EPHIN as Photon detector (CAU)

With the recent implementation of the EPHIN GEANT4 model, computation of the response to photons has been performed. The first silicon detector A is the one that is most sensitive to the photon flux. Taking into account the nominal threshold of the detector of 30 keV the expected count rate increases are a factor of 50 lower than the observed one. This is illustrated in *Figure 1-16*. On the left hand side, a RHESSI photon spectrum is shown. This is used as input into the simulation and results in the count rates obtained on the right-hand side as function of the energy threshold in the first detector. The measured count rate is indicated by the vertical line. A good agreement is obtained if the threshold is significantly lowered.

Figure 1-16 – A RHESSI photon spectrum that is used as input (panel on the left hand side) and the resulting counting rate as a function of energy threshold (panel on the right hand side)

This effect was found to be systematic so that the instrument was brought into a failure mode that allows it to determine the effective threshold of the detector. In agreement with the photon analysis a lower threshold of 15 keV was found. Work is in progress to understand the behaviour and to implement an efficiency model for energy losses between 15 and 30 keV.

Task 3-7. ERNE and SIXS as a relativistic particle instrument (UTU, CAU)

The UTU team has studied the response of two hardware coincidence counters of the ERNE High Energy Detector (HED) by comparing their counting rates to observations by the IMP-8/GME experiment. These counters are sensitive to particles penetrating the whole HED detector stack. The GEANT4 simulations indicate that the effective energy range of the counter channels is above 100 MeV (see Task 2.2 reported here above), but the exact range is still somewhat uncertain because the accurate values for the triggering levels of the various detector elements are unknown and have to be determined utilising pulse height data collected during the mission.

The log-log correlation of ERNE counters and IMP-8 proton fluxes in channels >100 MeV was studied for five events in the time range that both instruments took observations. The correspondences were fitted with

$$\log R_{\text{HED}} = C + m \log I_{\text{GME}}$$

using the RANSAC method that rejects the clear outliers from the fit. Here *C* and *m* are fitting parameters. The values of *m* close to unity implied the best linear correspondence between the datasets. In addition, we computed the values of χ^2 per degrees of freedom for the data with the

assumption that the two datasets are linearly correlated with zero offset (i.e., that $m = 1$). These two methods point towards the effective energy of the penetrating particle counter to be in the range of 166–202 MeV (see the *Figure 1-17* below, from Antila, V., MSc thesis, in preparation, University of Turku, 2024). The m value closest to unity was achieved using the GME energy channel at 166 MeV and the lowest value of $\chi^2 / \text{d.o.f.}$ was obtained with the GME energy channel at 202 MeV.

Figure 1-17 – Evolution of m as a function of energy for 5 SEP events and their mean case

The corresponding values of C were also computed and converted to effective geometric factors of the HED channel ($G\Delta E$ [$\text{cm}^2 \text{sr MeV}$] = 10^{-C}) if assumed to be equivalent to the corresponding GME channel. The geometric factor $G\Delta E$ is the conversion factor needed for converting the counting rates into differential intensities at an effective energy, i.e.,

$$I_{\text{HED}}(E_{\text{eff}}) = R_{\text{HED}}/G\Delta E.$$

The values of $G\Delta E$ [$\text{cm}^2 \text{sr MeV}$] are listed in *Table 1-5* below for the 166-MeV and 202-MeV channels. We can see that the variations are very large from one event to another and there is no clear consensus value obtained. We speculate that this could be because the true effective energy is somewhere between the two GME channels, which would amplify the scatter due to spectral variability, but also the deviation of the value of m from unity affects the result. Further studies are on-going.

Table 1-5: The values of $G\Delta E$ [$\text{cm}^2 \text{sr MeV}$]

E_{eff} [MeV]	2001 Green	2001 Blue	2001 Orange	1997 Purple	1998 Red	Mean	Sigma
165.57	3993.6	353.36	266.67	2598.5	606.06	564.04	733.59
202.34	2851.5	575.01	479.34	2040.8	1042.9	888.89	1464.7

The work on the BepiColombo / SIXS instrument observations has not yet started.

Task 3-8. EPHIN, HET and KET as a relativistic particle instrument (CAU)

Concerning EPHIN, progress has been made and is reported above in Task 2.2 for response functions and their application in 3.4 and 3.5. The same methods will be applied for Ulysses KET and SoLO HET.

Progress has been achieved concerning the simulation of energetic particles (protons, helium and electrons) in the energy range from an MeV up to 10 GeV including the spacecraft structure for SOHO/EPHIN. The response functions of SSD F to protons and helium are shown in *Figure 1-18*. While the first increase is due to particles entering the instrument from “free space” the second one gives the contribution due to the spacecraft shielding and the third increase is due to the increasing secondary particle production.

Figure 1-18 – The response functions of SSD F to protons and helium

The same investigations are ongoing for the Chandra EPHIN and the SOLO HET.

During the reporting period, all tasks within WP3 made significant progress. Notably, cross-calibration between spaceborne datasets, and where necessary, in conjunction with ground-based observations, was conducted, with the work carried out in WP2 also facilitating advancements in WP3. Progress was achieved in the calibration of SOHO/EPHIN with low-orbiting spectrometers AMS-02 and PAMELA, laying the groundwork for the upcoming deliverable D3.1. Overall, the work across all tasks established a strong foundation for the deliverables scheduled (mostly) for the second year of the project (Table 1-3).

1.2.4 Work Package 4

Work Package 4 (WP4) provides key properties of coronal shocks, based on context observations and related modelling, solar hard X-ray and gamma-ray observations for high-energy SEP events analysed in detail in SPEARHEAD. On top of that, it details the structure of ICMEs and offers a list of large-scale solar-wind structures to complement the catalogues created within the project. *Table 1-6* below summarizes the Deliverables of WP4.

Table 1-6: WP4 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D4.1	CME event selection	A report detailing which CME events were selected to fit the shock and flux ropes in 3-D and the rationale for this selection.	UT3	6
D4.2	Radio, X-ray and gamma-ray analysis	A report detailing the analysis of radio, hard X-ray and gamma-ray data.	UT3	12
D4.3	3-D shock catalogue	A report detailing the results of 3-D fitting the shocks and a small catalogue of the 3-D shock parameters exploitable by the whole community.	UT3	22
D4.4	3-D shock and flux-rope modelling verification	A report detailing the comparison between the 3-D modelling of shock and flux ropes and in situ data	UT3	26
D4.5	3-D flux-rope catalogue	A report on 3-D fitting the flux rope and a small catalogue of the 3-D Flux Rope parameters exploitable by the whole community	UT3	30

Task 4-1. Establishing a of CME events to be modelled in Tasks 4.2 and 4.3 (Lead UT3, partners: CAU, UTU)

A list of CME-SEP events was established in this Task. This resulted from a preliminary analysis of each event in order to isolate important high-energy processes that **SPEARHEAD** aims to better understand, based on its scientific questions (see WP5). In addition to being linked with high-energy radiation detected in situ, the events had to meet several other criteria. This included being well observed, allowing the WP4 team to analyse and model the evolution of potential accelerators like shocks. Further indicators of high-energy radiation, such as gamma-ray and hard X-ray emissions, were also taken into account. Lastly the spacecraft's orbital configuration was assessed. As a result the list of high energy radiation solar events for further study within the project was compiled (*Figure 1-19*). This process along with the details of the list were included in **D4.1**

PRIORITY ORDER	PRIORITY CAT	EVENT DATE	GLE?	FORBUSH DECREASE?	EUV/WHITE-LIGHT OBSERVATIONS	HXR/GAMMA ?	INTENSE SEP?	INTERESTING ASPECT ?	FAR SIDE	TYPE II?	EARTH DIRECTED CME?	IN SITU CME FR/SHOCK K?
10	P1 (2024-2025)	21-03-2011	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	NO HXR/GAMMA	YES AT STEREO-A	ISOLATED, WIDESPREAD SEP	YES	YES	NO	STEREO-A
13	P2 (2025-2026)	07-03-2012	SUB-GLE	YES LONG LASTING	VERY GOOD	GAMMA EVENT	yes at EPHIN	NICE SHOCK IN IMAGERY	NO	?	YES	L1
4	P1 (2024-2025)	12-7-2012	NO	SIMPLE SHORT	VERY GOOD	NO GAMMA	NO	ISOLATED, ERNE GOOD DATA	NO	?	YES	L1
6	P2 (2025-2026)	23-7-2012	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	NO FAR SIDE	CARRINGTON LIKE	HIGH RADIATION PRESSURE	YES	YES	NO	STEREO-A
5	P1 (2024-2025)	17-05-2012	71	NO	VERY GOOD	GAMMA EVENT	YES	GLE, ISOLATED EVENT, CONNECTIVITY FR.	NO	YES	YES	L1
7	P2 (2025-2026)	01-09-2014	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	GAMMA EVENT	YES	ISOLATED, WIDESPREAD SEP, ERNE, STEREO, GAMMA EVENT	YES (VERY)	YES	NO	NO
12	P1 (2025-2026)	20-06-2015	NO	YES LONG LASTING	GOOD	NO GAMMA	NO (@ Earth)	COMPOUND STREAM	NO	?	YES	L1
11	P2 (2025-2026)	10-09-2017	72	NO	GOOD	GAMMA-RAY	YES	ISOLATED WEST LMB	NOISH	YES	NO	?
3	P2 (2025-2026)	17-7-2021	NO	NO	VERY GOOD	GAMMA EVENT	? (NO @ Earth)	FAR BEHIND THE LIMB EVENT	YES (VERY)	?	NO	?
8	P2 (2025-2026)	28-10-2021	73	NO	VERY GOOD	GAMMA EVENT	YES	STRONG GLE	NO	YES	?	?
9	P1 (2024-2025)	2-11-2021	NO	YES	VERY GOOD	NO GAMMA	NOT INTENSE	NICE FD, MULTI-SPACECRAFT	NO	?	yes	L1, Solo
2	P1 (2024-2025)	11-05-2024	74	YES, strong	GOOD	NOT YET AVAILABLE	YES	GLE COINCIDES WITH FD, MAGNO	NO	?	YES	?
1	P1 (2024-2025)	08-06-2024	?	Unlikely	VERY GOOD	?	?	STRONG SEP, DIRECTED AT PSP	NO	?	YES	?

Figure 1-19 – List of events that are considered of highest priority for the first case studies of the project

Task 4-2. Identifications of radio, hard X-rays and gamma-ray signatures of the strong CME events (Lead UT3, Partners: UTU)

The electromagnetic properties of the candidate solar sources of the different SEPs provide important information on the properties that may be at play during the acceleration of SEPs in the solar atmosphere as well as their transport from the Sun to the points of in situ measurements. A review of the available radio, hard X-rays and gamma ray data for the events selected in Task 4-1 is on-going. Two main tasks are underway, one consisting in providing an estimate of the solar source (flare timing and intensity, CME properties, shock occurrence) to each intense SEP listed in the ERNE and EPHIN SEP catalogue provided by WP5 (*being the basis for D5.1*), the other is a more in-depth analysis of the events given in the previous table for a subset of events of particular interest to the science of particle acceleration and transport.

Solar source properties of the ERNE/EPHIN SEP catalogue: the electromagnetic properties that were considered for each event were so far were:

- the GOES soft X-ray measurements,
- the hard X-ray measurements from STIX,
- the radio spectragrams provided from STEREO-SWAVES and WIND-WAVES,
- the gamma-ray data from FERMI LAT by considering two detection techniques (light bucket and Maximum likelihood),
- the CME signatures from coronagraphic observations (LASCO C2 and C3).

From the onset of each SEP event measured by ERNE we then did a preliminary backmapping that will need to be improved at a later stage perhaps from more advanced velocity dispersion analysis. This backmapping provided an estimate of the departure time of particles at the Sun which was then considered as a reference time to search for solar phenomena such as flares and CMES.

The results of this analysis are given in dedicated columns of the ERNE/EPHIN catalogue (provided by WP5) which contains 176 SEP events as of today and of which a subset of the latest 2024 period is given in Figure 1-20.

SOHO/ERNE > 100 MeV SEP list													CME		GLEs								
No	Identifier	Year	Month	Day	Date UT	Hour	Minute	Second	Background mean unit?	X-ray flare				Radio Type III	Radio Type II	Gamma Rays	Speed km/s	Width degree	Source	Name			
										Start Date	Time	Peak Date	Time								Class	Position	Observer
160	20240129T044000	2024	1	29		4		40	0.346.0	2024-01-29	3:54:00	2024-01-29	4:38:00	M6.8	N28W86	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	NO	NO	1554	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
161	20240209T143000	2024	2	9		14		30	0.353.0	2024-02-09	12:53:00	2024-02-09	13:14:00	X3.4	S37W85	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	SWAVES	LAT (LB / ML)	2782	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
162	20240217T004000	2024	2	17		0		40	0.443.0	2024-02-19	22:56:00	2024-02-19	23:07:00	M9.07	S17W177	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	SWAVES	NO	817	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
163	20240217T071000	2024	2	17		7		10	0.429.0	2024-02-12	3:23:00	2024-02-12	3:48:00	M6.5	S13W05	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	SWAVES	NO	2792	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
164	20240216T073000	2024	2	16		7		30	0.357.7	2024-02-16	6:42:00	2024-02-16	6:53:00	X2.5	S19W82	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	NO	LAT (LB / ML)	615	PARTIAL HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
165	20240323T093000	2024	3	23		2		50	0.341.0	2024-03-23	0:58:00	2024-03-23	1:33:00	X1.1	S14E15	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	SWAVES, WAVEE	NO DATA	1470	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
166	20240510T105000	2024	5	11		1		50	0.358.8	2024-05-11	1:10:00	2024-05-11	1:23:00	X2.8	S15W65	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	SWAVES, WAVEE	NO DATA	1614	HALO, ASCO CME cat	GLE74	
167	20240513T170000	2024	5	13		17		0	0.345.6	2024-05-13	08:48:00	2024-05-13	09:44:00	M6.6	S17W81	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	SWAVES, WAVEE	NO DATA	1680	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
168	20240520T103000	2024	5	20		10		35	0.309.9	U	U	U	U	U	U	SWAVES, WAVES	NO	NO	U	U	U	/	
169	20240607T235000	2024	6	7		23		50	0.312.5	2024-06-08	1:23:00	2024-06-08	1:49:00	M6.8	S17W72	GOES	SWAVES	SWAVES	NO	1427	HALO, ASCO CME cat	/	
170	20240611T220000	2024	6	11		22		20	0.375.5	U	U	U	U	U	U	SWAVES, WAVES	NO	NO DATA	U	U	U	/	
171	20240723T040000	2024	7	23		0		40	0.355.0	2024-07-22	23:32	2024-07-23	1:00:00	X14	T80	STIX HXR	NO	NO	NO	NA	NA	NA	/
172	20240805T143000	2024	8	5		14		35	0.328.3	2024-08-05	13:24:00	2024-08-05	13:40:00	X1.7	S10W88	GOES	SWAVES, WAVES	NO	NO DATA	NA	NA	NA	/

Figure 1-20 – Subset list of intense SEPs measured by ERNE and their estimated solar sources (X-ray flare, CMES)

Each SEP event has an identifier (two left-hand columns), the ERNE catalogue provided by WP5 an estimate of the onset of each SEP event.

This subset illustrates nicely the different types of possible associations between SEPs and the difficulties encountered when making such associations. For some SEPs, the onset was unfortunately missed out (for example event 169) due to instrumental outage. For certain SEPs a clear link with specific solar flares measured by GOES could be easily established because the flare occurred in isolation such as for events 161 and 169. For other events, like event 162 there were many solar flares around the estimated onset times: to flag these uncertain events a question mark has been placed in the catalogue for future consideration. Some SEP events originate in events that occurred on the far side of the Sun and no GOES SXR could be detected but for those the STIX instrument on Solar Orbiter was sometimes taking HXR data and a clear flare source could be identified: an example is given for event 171 that was associated with an estimated X14 SXR flare (*Figure 1-21*).

Figure 1-21 – Solar Orbiter STIX detection (left: image, right: light curves) of the far-side flare associated with the ERNE SEP event 171

These SEPs are of particular interest because the flare is occulted yet a clear SEP is measured in situ near Earth. Finally, some SEPs could not be related to any specific powerful flare nor CME and these events are marked by a U for ‘undetermined’ solar source.

The same procedure followed for the SEP-flare pairing was considered for CME properties where the maximum speed and form of the CME (halo, partial halo) observed by the LASCO C2 and C3 coronagraphs are reported for each SEP event. These properties were obtained from the official LASCO CME catalogue. A weblink to movies of each identified CME event is also given in this first form of the catalogue.

These SEP-solar source associations are well underway and will be soon augmented with other electromagnetic signatures such as the occurrence of radio bursts and gamma-ray events.

Solar source properties of the events selected in D4.1: the aim here is to provide more in-depth analysis, Therefore, collaborative work is underway with the Solar Orbiter STIX instrument team to study HXR signatures of the most recent solar energetic events (17-07-2021, 08-06-2024, 11-05-2024, 23-07-2024). RHESSI HXR data will also be considered when we study older events. In addition, analyses of radio bursts and gamma-ray emissions are also on-going for a subset of events that were observed by radio spectrographs and gamma-ray detectors.

Task 4-3. Three dimensional modelling of CME shocks (Lead UT3)

This modelling task is underway on the events that were selected as of the highest priority in Task 4.1. We have performed 3-D fits of shock waves driven by the CME of 11th of May 2024 (see *Figure 1-22*) and of the 8th of June 2024. For these first 3-D fits we exploit all available coronal imaging SPEARHEAD Deliverable D1.3

taken by spacecraft located near 1AU (STEREO-A and SDO/SoHO). The 3-D triangulation procedure consists in fitting simple ellipsoidal structures to coronal images taken simultaneously from different vantage points. More details on the technique are given in [Rouillard et al. \(2016\)](#).

Figure 1-22 - Three-dimensional fit of the shock wave associated with the recent 11th of May 2024 CME

The next step is to exploit coronal and heliospheric modelling to obtain the parameters of the background corona into which the shock is propagating and derive the 3-D shock parameters (*Figure 1-23*). This modelling generally assumes that the corona has reached a stationary state where background parameters at a given position do not change with time. In this first stage of the task we exploit the background 3-D MHD model solution delivered routinely by Predictive Sciences Inc (<https://www.predsci.com/mhdweb/home.php>).

The final step consists in extracting shock parameters along specific magnetic field lines of interest that are connected to the different spacecraft making in situ measurements of SEPs. *Figure 1-23* shows the result of extracting the Alfvén Mach number along magnetic field lines connected to Earth and Solar Orbiter, while *Figure 1-24* presents the evolution of the shock properties for the field lines connected to Earth for this event.

Figure 1-23 - Distribution of the Alfvén Mach number at the surface of the modelled shock wave for the 11th of May 2024 CME event and magnetic field lines connected to different spacecraft.

Figure 1-24 - Evolution of the shock parameters (shock speed, Alfvén Mach, Fast-mode Mach, de-Hoffman Teller shock speed, upstream Alfvén speed) modelled along magnetic field lines connected to Earth during the 11th of May 2024 (GLE74).

The magnetic connectivity of Earth and SoLO was modelled here by assuming that the interplanetary magnetic field is a Parker spiral. Yet the analysis of in situ data shows that at the onset of the GLE the interplanetary magnetic field was highly disturbed by the outward propagation of other ICMEs. The GLE onset occurred within a clear magnetic cloud which means that the energetic particles

propagated through a magnetic flux rope from the Sun to 1AU. The next step in this case study is to model the evolution of this magnetic cloud (Task 4.4) and then model the transport of energetic particles accelerated at the shock through this cloud.

Task 4-4: Three dimensional modelling of CME flux ropes (Lead UT3)

Modelling of the CME flux ropes associated with the 11 May 2024 has begun and will proceed in the next months.

We are also planning to model the flux rope propagation of another event relevant to the modelling of the Forbush decrease of 12 July 2012 planned as part of WP5.

Task 4-5: Comparison of modelled shock waves and flux ropes with in situ measurements (Lead UT3)

An initial analysis of the complex ICME flux ropes and shocks measured in situ associated with the powerful 11 May 2024 is underway and will be exploited in conjunction with Tasks 4.3 and 4.5 to deliver a full case study of the 11 May 2024. This analysis also forms the basis of the interplanetary flux rope modelling planned in Task 4-4.

We have also started analysing the interplanetary signature of the CME of 2024-06-07/08 event that impacted Parker Solar Probe around the 2024-06-11 when located 110Rs from the Sun. A summary of some preliminary data is given in *Figure 1-25*.

Figure 1-25 - Preliminary analysis of interplanetary conditions for the 2024-06-11 strong SEP event with the orbital configuration (top left), the in situ signature of the ICME at Parker Solar Probe (top left), the CME observed by LASCO (bottom left) and the SEP measured by GOES (bottom right)

During this first reporting period WP4 submitted the assigned Deliverable (D4.1; Table 1-6) on time, as per the DoA and the GA. Furthermore, focused work has been performed towards the fulfilment of D4.2

1.2.5 Work Package 5

SPEARHEAD has set three science questions: (see Section 1.1), which will be answered through a detailed analysis of very high-energy particle observations from the most important heliophysics missions combined with ground based measurements, provided by the project. In doing so, **Work Package 5 (WP5)** will provide catalogues of high energy SEP events and ICME related Forbush decreases. It will further perform statistical analysis and will focus on particular case studies of interest.

Table 1-7: WP5 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D5.1	Catalogue of >100 MeV proton events	First release of a comprehensive catalogue of >100 MeV proton events based on SPEARHEAD datasets	UTU	12
D5.2	Catalogue of ultrarelativistic electron events	First release of a catalogue of ultrarelativistic electron events based on SPEARHEAD datasets	CAU	15
D5.3	List of ICME-related Forbush decreases	List of ICME-related Forbush decreases compiled from SPEARHEAD datasets	OH	18
D5.4	Synthesis of scientific results	A report on statistical analyses of the catalogued events and synthesis of the scientific analyses of SPEARHEAD	NOA	34

In this period the following work has been performed towards these goals, per Task:

Task 5-1: Analysis of >100 MeV proton events (lead: UTU, partners: CAU, NOA, IRAP, UOULU)

UTU produced the first version of the event list of >100 MeV protons based on the penetrating particle counter of ERNE/HED, scanning data between May 1996 – August 2024 using a moving background window and detecting events that are above a threshold relative to that. The preliminary list contains 176 events, for which the onset time was detected using the SERPENTINE onset tool (Palmroos et al., 2022), but the final number may still change when the methodology is tuned to be somewhat more sensitive and increases due to other than solar sources are removed. An example of a detected event is shown below (Figure 1-26):

Figure 1-26 - The onset time determination of the SEP event on 17-05-2001 from SOHO/ERNE >100 MeV ions counting rate

At present, this catalogue further includes the fluence and peak flux from SOHO/EPHIN at a comparable (>100 MeV) energy. In addition, solar associations have been established in terms of solar flares (i.e. soft X-rays peak flux, location), coronal mass ejections (width, speed) for the majority of these very high energy events. Current ongoing work focuses on CME-shock reconstructions/fits. In addition, a column indicating whether or if the particular SEP event is a GLE or a sub-GLE has been added, highlighting these cases.

Task 5-2: Analysis of ultrarelativistic solar electron events (lead: CAU, partners: UTU, IRAP)

Work has been carried out investigating the EPHIN and KET flux. At multi MeV energies the variation of the Jovian electron flux can be as high as the one from small relativistic electron events. Event onset time as well as peak time and flux are determined utilising the SERPENTINE onset tool (*Palmroos et al., 2022*). An example event is shown in the figure below (*Figure 1-27*).

Figure 1-27 - Similar to Figure 1-26 but for the electrons of ~ 5 MeV during the SEP event on 09-05-1998 from Ulysses/KET flux

Work has also been performed to identify major solar energetic electron events that were measured at energies above 10 MeV by the HET aboard Solo.

An inspection of the historic Ulysses KET data with electron energies above 10 MeV is ongoing. The Ulysses trajectory is characterised by the Jovian flyby in 1992 and the distant flyby in 2004. During these periods a large number of Jovian electron events were observed. These events also cause an increase in the above 10 MeV electron flux. In order to separate them from Solar Electron Events (SEEs) we utilised the KET proton channel that measures 30 to 120 MeV protons. *Figure 1-28* displays a Jovian event and a SEE on the left panel and the right panel, respectively.

Figure 1-28 - A Jovian electron event (panel on the left) and an SEP event (panel on the right) observed by Ulysses/KET

In contrast to the left panel the right one shows that the proton channel (black curve) increases simultaneously with the electron. Below in *Figure 1-29* are shown all major SEEs identified so far.

Figure 1-29 - The Ulysses trajectory (radial distance and latitude - top panel) for the whole mission and the identified SEE events on the background of Ulysses orbit (bottom panel)

Task 5-3. Analysis of sub-GLE events (lead: UOULU, partners: CAU, UTU, NOA, INAF)

This task aims to derive the spectral and angular characteristics of so-called sub-GLEs, i.e. events that are SEPs that cause enhancements of the count rate of only high-altitude polar NM stations. The task started at M6 with NM records preparation of validation of existing datasets and careful study of world data center NM records. In addition, several events are selected for cross-checking and inter-calibration with space probe measurements, specifically the notable event on 7 March 2012, which was measured by GOES and AMS02. Most importantly, we identified two new sub-GLEs, found in data of NMs at the South Pole and Vostok stations, namely the events on 09 June 1968 and 27 February 1969. For this purpose, we used two groups of NMs, the first consisting of two high-altitude polar stations necessary to define a statistically significant increase in station count rates related to a SEP event, whilst the second incorporated sea-level polar NMs necessary to reveal the lack of a signal corresponding to the event. The selected stations were SOPO (South Pole), VSTK (Vostok) as high-altitude polar ones, while THUL (Thule) and MCMD (McMurdo) in the northern and southern hemispheres, respectively. For the analysis, we selected the *Spaceship Earth* NM stations. The SEP event on 09 June 1968 was observed by satellite AIMP-1 as an enhancement of the intensity of protons $J(> 60 \text{ MeV})$. The increase started at 09:35 UT, reached its maximum at about 12 UT and lasted for more than one day. SOPO and VSTK revealed simultaneous increases in count rate with the magnitude of +1.28% and +0.97% over the GCR background, respectively. The SEP event on 27 February 1969 was observed as an increase in the proton intensity $J(> 60\text{MeV})$ with the onset at 15

UT, maximum at 19 UT, and ending at about 20 UT on the next day. We found increases associated with this SEP signal in the neutron monitor data of SOPO and VSTK with magnitudes of +1.58% and +1.82% over the GCR background. The analysis of both events was performed with full scale modeling similar to GLE analysis using the NM records using full reconstruction and simplified approach, the latter not accounting the anisotropy, (see [Koldobskiy& Mishev 2022](#); [Poluianov et al., 2024](#)). An example of the derived spectra and fluences is shown in the Figure below.

Figure 1-30 - Spectra of the intensity $j(R)$ for different periods of the sub-GLE event (left panel) and fluence (time- and energy integrated), right panel) $F(> E)$ on 09 June 1968. The time intervals in the left panel are given in UT. The grey line and shaded area indicate the GCR background with the heliospheric modulation ϕ of 752 MV in June 1968.

The analysis of the 7 March 2012 sub-GLE event is currently in progress. All the necessary preliminary computations, namely magnetospheric modeling of the asymptotic cones of the NM stations considered for the analysis, data validation, and GOES data were performed and collected.

Task 5-4: ICME related Forbush decreases (lead: OH, partners: NOA, IRAP)

This task is devoted to building an extensive catalogue of Forbush decreases across the heliosphere, which will be used for statistical analysis as well as application of Forbush decrease model ForbMod (WP7). The task started at month 6 with preparation of GUI which will be used to obtain the catalogue. Although the GUI was not initially planned, we opted for it nevertheless because we wish to add more datasets (outside those planned for this project) and possibly apply different versions of models (beyond current ForbMod). This will not only ease our measurement and analysis but will also be made open for the research community to utilise for independent studies. Currently, in GUI implemented are datasets from near-Earth spacecraft (Wind, ACE and SOHO/EPHIN) and SPEARHEAD Deliverable D1.3

Figure 1-31 - A screenshot of the GUI

Solar Orbiter and first measurements are performed (cca 50 events). The results were disseminated at the European Cosmic Ray Symposium (ECRS). In the upcoming months we will implement data from Ulysses (already obtained from CAU), neutron monitors and finally MSL/RAD. As added value to the project, we plan to also include data from Helios and Parker Solar Probe spacecraft. *Figure 1-31* shows an example event in GUI from Wind/SOHO EPHIN data (from top-to-bottom: magnetic field, plasma, cosmic ray counts). The bottom panel is reserved for neutron monitors.

Task 5-5. Effect of ICMEs on cosmic ray propagation (lead: INAF, partners: NOA)

This task has not started yet.

It concerns the application of an information theory technique to assess the influence of the solar wind disturbances on GCR intensity during Forbush decreases.

A set of Forbush decreases events will be considered along with solar wind plasma and magnetic field parameters., i.e. an ensemble of independent time series, that allows us to investigate the information flow between different physical quantities and to quantify how it varies during the different phases of the FDs. The Forbush decreases events will be selected from the list of ICME-related FDs, realized in Task 5.-4.

Task 5-6. Synthesis of the scientific results on high-energy particles (lead: NOA, partners: UTU, CAU)

Although this Task has not formally started yet since it concerns the synthesis of the outputs from previous Tasks, the selection of the CME list to be analysed in detail by the **SPEARHEAD** project in **D4.1** with its priority order, based on the scientific merit of each event and strategic development of the project, paved the way for the scientific analysis. Several such events are under investigation, including for example the recent series of the May 2024 events which nicely combine ICMEs-FDs-Geomagnetic storms and SEPs and GLEs. In fact, first results of this ongoing work will be presented in the upcoming ESWW.

During the first reporting period, WP5 focused on the scanning of datasets to support the development of high-energy particle catalogues for the upcoming deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 (Table 1-7). Additionally, foundational work was initiated for D5.3, including the creation of a graphical user interface (GUI) and its population with plasma and particle data. Work related to D4.1, along with the significant events of May and June 2024, has also led to the initial synthesis of research findings within the Consortium, in line with the expectations for D5.4.

1.2.6 Work Package 6

Work Package 6 (WP6) coordinates the tools development and data product distribution in SPEARHEAD, while generating the necessary interface to ensure effective distribution of these tools and the high-level datasets that will be outputted by the project. *Table 1-8* below summarises the Deliverables of WP6.

Table 1-8: WP6 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D6.1	SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan	A Detailed Plan on SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Activities	UTU	6
D6.2	SPEARHEAD GitHub repository	A GitHub repository for SPEARHEAD Python tools	UTU	12
D6.3	JupyterHub for SPEARHEAD Tools	A JupyterHub for running the SPEARHEAD tools without having to install them locally	UTU	18
D6.4	SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Report	A report describing the tools and datasets released through SPEARHEAD services	UTU	34

Task 6-1: SPEARHEAD tools and data development plan (Lead: UTU, partners: CAU, SPARC; UPS; UOULU)

The main work in WP6 has been as planned directed to Task 6-1 that cumulated in the creation of the **SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan (D6.1)**. In this document, we have laid out our plans for the development and release of the tools and data products that are planned to be worked on within the other work packages in the coming months. **Deliverable 6.1** describes what kind of software is foreseen to be created by the consortium as well as common practices the project aims to adhere to in the development of it, like version control, documentation, testing and verification, or how the distribution is planned, and how user feedback should be collected. Regarding data products to be released through SPEARHEAD, the Development Plan (**D6.1**) lists technical details that we agreed on, like different formats and licences in/under which they should be provided, the foreseen distribution channels as well as procedures regarding validation, feedback, and versioning. Following these guidelines throughout the different work packages will ensure the adherence of FAIR principles and maximise the impact of the project.

Task 6-2: Distributing SPEARHEAD data products (Lead: UTU, partners: CAU, SPARC; UPS; UOULU)

Work has mainly been carried out in planning this task. The results of this process are laid out in the SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan (**D6.1**)

Task 6-3: Distributing SPEARHEAD tools (Lead: UTU, partners: partners: CAU, SPARC; UPS; UOULU)

Work has mainly been carried out in planning this task. The results of this process are laid out in the SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan (**D6.1**). At **SPEARHEAD's Workshop #1** in June 2024, further discussion with a representative of *ESA/Datalabs* took place, which resulted in first test runs of using the system. This will be helpful at a later stage of the project, when the actual SPEARHEAD

SPEARHEAD Deliverable D1.3

tools will be distributed. In addition **SPEARHEAD's Github** was implemented and will be populated with tools produced by the project, as work progresses.

Task 6-4: Testing and feedback (Lead: UTU, partners: all)

This task has not started yet.

During this first reporting period WP6 submitted the assigned Deliverable (D6.1; Table 1-8) on time, as per the DoA and the GA. Further work was undertaken in view of D6.2, with the implementation of SPEARHEAD's Github repository.

1.2.7 Work Package 7

Work Package 7 (WP7) provides a direct link of the project's outputs to the needs of the planned and/or under-design missions of nowadays, through e.g., the characterization of the particle radiation environment at different energies in the Heliosphere via the exploitation of the novel **SPEARHEAD** high-energy particle data and tools. *Table 1-9* below summarises the Deliverables of WP7.

Table 1-9: WP7 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D7.1	Particle radiation environment specification	Report on the particle radiation environment based on SPEARHEAD data products	INAF	30
D7.2	Forbush decrease model for flux ropes	Report on the application of the Forbush decrease model for flux ropes utilising SPEARHEAD data products	OH	33
D7.3	Algorithms for event detection	A report describing the outcome of designing machine learning algorithms for SEP event detection and automated identification of FDs	INAF	36
D7.4	SEP forecasting model	Report on the update of NOAA's PROSPER SEP forecasting model using SPEARHEAD data products	NOA	36

WP7 starts on Month 18 of the project and thus work has been planned but not executed for most of the Tasks of the WP. Nonetheless, the interrelation of WP5 to WP2 and WP7 allowed for some first steps to be implemented. See details here below:

Task 7.2 - Application of the Forbush decreases model for flux ropes (lead:OH):

The work carried out in WP7 is to be started at month 18. Nevertheless, preparatory actions are already on the way. This task is devoted to application of the model ForbMod to the extensive list of Forbush decreases in the heliosphere, which will be compiled in WP5, and will use response functions provided by WP2. ForbMod analysis on a preliminary sample is performed as a proof-of-concept and guideline in possible pitfalls. This was already disseminated at several conferences to get feedback from the scientific community. Parametric analysis is underway, especially regarding the sensitivity to response functions and measurements errors. A GUI is underway (developed in the scope of WP5) which will also include ForbMod application for a faster, easier and more robust ForbMod analysis.

During this first reporting period WP7 has not started its implementation, rather participated in the planning and specification preparatory phase in close collaboration to WP2 and WP5.

1.2.8 Work Package 8

Work Package 8 (WP8) responsibility falls on the effective communication and dissemination of results to lead user communities, the wider scientific community and Agencies; the providing of plans for the exploitation of results and public outreach and educational activities. *Table 1-10* below summarizes the Deliverables of WP8.

Table 1-10: WP8 Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	Lead	Deliv. month
D8.1	Project website	Public website of the project established	NOA	2
D8.2	Dissemination and Communication Plan	SPEARHEAD's Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan	NOA	6
D8.3	Educational material on solar eruptions	Master level course material on high-energy particles related to solar eruptions	UTU	24
D8.4	White paper on future instruments and missions	White paper on future instrument and mission concepts that would fill the gaps of data that remain after SPEARHEAD	CAU	34
D8.5	SPEARHEAD Workshop and School	Report on the SPEARHEAD Workshop and School	CAU	35

Task 8-1: Public website of the consortium (NOA)

The **SPEARHEAD** project started on **1 January 2024**. The public website of the project was released in the second month of the project at <https://spearhead-he.eu>. Details on the sections, architectural design, durability and maintenance are included in **D8.1**

Task 8-2: Dissemination and communication of results (Lead NOA; Partners: all)

The **SPEARHEAD** project, within the Reporting Period, concluded the initial *Preparation phase* and continued into its *Main analysis phase*. Special emphasis was put on the *first Pillar* of the project that concerns *Data & Analysis Methods* and is distributed over WP2, WP3 and WP4. Hence, a significant part of SPEARHEAD's results in this time period stemmed from these WPs. Nonetheless, several other ongoing research efforts concerning WP5, WP6 and preparatory actions on WP7 were also initiated. **SPEARHEAD** had a continuous presence in international conferences and workshops.

As per the communication of the projects' results, the main communication point of the project is its website (<https://spearhead-he.eu>), which was implemented early on (see **D1.1**). In conjunction with the implementation of the project's portal a series of communication tools were established. These included *social media* (i.e. Facebook, Instagram and X accounts), a *YouTube* channel, *news section* in the website which is directly linked to the feeds of the social media accounts, a *Zenodo* dedicated community and a *GitHub* repository for the project (all of which are linked to the main portal). All these means of the project ensure the efficient communication and dissemination of its results to the specified user communities (*Figure 1-32*).

Figure 1-32 - Composite figure with the communication and dissemination tools already implemented and in use by SPEARHEAD

Task 8-3. Planning of exploitation of results (Lead NOA; Partners: all)

Once the communication channels, means and tools were implemented and set into operation (see Task 8-2), a detailed plan for the dissemination and communication of the projects' results to key target audiences was put together. In particular, six main Key Target Groups for the project were identified and tailored communication measures were identified for each of these. The details of the planning are included in **D8.2**. This provides the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* of the Project, whose purpose is to detail the Project's approach on what needs to be communicated and why, to whom, when, how, and by whom. As described in Task 8-2 and Task 8-4 communication and dissemination activities follow this plan aiming at maximising the impact of the project.

Work concerning D8.3, D8.4 and 8.5 has not started yet and is planned to be performed later in 2025

Task 8-4. Public outreach and education (Lead: NOA; Partners: CAU, UTU, UOULU, IRAP, INAF, OH)

Particular communication activities in this period involved interviews in media (newspapers, public journal articles), a TV appearance, a public outreach presentation for the public and discussion meetings with schools (see the relevant *Communication activities* listed in the *EU portal* for details).

Additionally, the News section in the SPEARHEAD portal provided up-to-date information on the project and its results. This news was consequently disseminated via the social media of **SPEARHEAD**.

During this first reporting period WP8 submitted the assigned Deliverables (D8.1 and D8.2; Table 1-10) on time, as per the DoA and the GA.

1.3 Impact

SPEARHEAD's outputs and strategic moves are in agreement with its initial planning, concerning impact. Key Target Groups (*Figure 1-33*) had been identified for the project, including the:

- **T1. Heliophysics community**
- **T2. Astrophysics community**
- **T3. Space weather community**
- **T4. Undergraduate and PhD students**
- **T5. Space Agencies and policymakers**
- **T6. The General public**

Figure 1-33 - The identified Key Target Groups for SPEARHEAD

For the **research communities** of **T1**, **T2** and **T3**, **SPEARHEAD**, in the reporting period, contributed to the advancement of knowledge and scientific understanding, providing new insights and methodologies that can be leveraged in future studies. This is a direct output of the work performed in **WP2-WP5**. Following, the plan outlined in the *DoA* **SPEARHEAD** disseminated its results to *international conferences, meetings and workshops*. Furthermore, collaboration among **SPEARHEAD** and other research projects was planned and achieved in this period (i.e. by taking part in the *EU Booster: Space Weather Cluster*) and from organizing common actions between research projects (i.e. in the upcoming *ESWW*).

Representatives of **T4** took part in the **Workshop #1** of **SPEARHEAD**, while some have been engaged in the project. In this way **T4** was impacted, as they gain exposure to cutting-edge research, enhancing their learning experience and providing opportunities for practical application of theoretical concepts. *A larger scale of impact for T4 will stem from outputs later in the project, e.g. the MSc course material and the hosting of a dedicated Summer School.*

T5 benefited from interactions in dedicated e.g. workshops in which the project's findings and/or progress were presented (i.e. **DASH**). In this way **T5** representatives gained access to improved practices and enhanced data analysis capabilities, which can drive efficiency and competitiveness in

their respective fields. **T5** will be further facilitated in the course of the project through the implementation of **WP7** and will utilize the research outcomes of **SPEARHEAD** to inform evidence-based decisions, leading to better regulatory frameworks and initiatives.

Furthermore, **T6** is impacted in this period, through increased awareness and understanding of the research themes, fostering a culture of science and encouraging community engagement. This has directly been planned in **SPEARHEAD** and achieved via its dissemination and communication channels (primarily through the website of **SPEARHEAD**) which are populated with relevant material and news on a regular basis.

2 Explanation of the resources

NOA: Use of resources at NOA follows the initial planning. The team assigned to various tasks within SPEARHEAD, distributed over several WPs, is in place. Additional support from members of the GRNET (Greek Research and Educational Network) who operate the cloud service for all Greek Universities and Research Centers (oceanos) through in-kind contributions as required.

UTU: Use of resources at UTU is according to the planning. The team working on different tasks of SPEARHEAD is in place and it is supported by in-kind contributions from members of the Space Research Laboratory, when needed.

CAU: Use of resources at CAU is according to the planning.

UOULU: The resources were used as planned. An in-kind contribution was provided in the form of research infrastructure and the work of Prof. Usoskin

UT3: Due to challenges encountered in hiring a postdoctoral researchers during the first year of the project, the staff at UT3-IRAP has carried out all necessary tasks until now.

SPARC: Use of resources at SPARC is according to the planning.

INAF: The cost of person month has increased substantially over the course of the past year due to an increase in academic rank/position of Dr. M. Laurenza and Dr. M. F. Marucci. In order to maintain the number of person months we included in the project Dr. Simone Benella, who has an expertise in cosmic rays and solar wind physics, suited to the INAF tasks. Therefore, *we claim the same budget with the same number of person months.*

OH: The cost of person month at OH increased substantially over the course of the past year (due to legislative and collective contractual agreements between public sector and government) and is expected to further increase (due to increase in academic rank/position of M. Dumbovic). *Therefore, we expect to claim the same budget, however with a reduced number of people per month. This will not affect the proposed work.*

3 Publications & Dissemination Activities

In accordance with DoA, **SPEARHEAD**, already from the beginning unfolded a realistic yet ambitious plan to maximise its impact. This was based on the different Key Target Groups (see Section 1.3) and was supported by many different dissemination activities. In particular:

First of all, SPEARHEAD had a strong presence in a series of international conferences: such as the *European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly* 14-19 April 2024 (<https://www.egu24.eu/>); *45th Committee on Space Research (COSPAR) Scientific Assembly*, 13-21 July 2024 (<https://www.cospar2024.org/>); the *28th European Cosmic Ray Symposium (ECRS)* 23-27 September 2024 (<https://oh.geof.unizg.hr/index.php/en/meetings/ecrs-2024/>), *IAUS 388: Solar and Stellar Coronal Mass Ejections* 05-10 May 2024 (<https://iausymposium.zyrosite.com/>) the *Solar Heliospheric and INterplanetary Environment (SHINE)* 12-16 August 2024 (<https://helioshine.org/>) and the *Data Analysis and Software in Heliophysics (DASH)* 14-16 October 2024 (<https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/ihdea/ihdea-dash-2024>).

During the reporting period, **Workshop #1** of the project was hosted by the **NOA**, as outlined in the DoA, from 11-13 June 2024 (<https://spearhead-he.eu/meetings/>), as a hybrid meeting (*Figure 3-1*). This was the first meeting that brought together the Partners of the project. On top of the CB meeting and the monitoring of the progress per WP, a day was further devoted to Scientific presentations. Members of the EAC, consortium members and scientists outside the consortium were invited to participate, present their work and engage in discussions related to the open Scientific Questions (SQs) to be tackled by SPEARHEAD. In the aftermath of the **Workshop #1**, scientific presentations and videos of these presentations were uploaded to the internal repository of SPEARHEAD and were made publicly available through the project's website.

Figure 3-1 - Composite figure with instances of the project's first Workshop

Finally, the first paper of the project: **Characterizing High-Energy Solar Proton Events with Energies Below and Above 100 MeV** by Ameri et al. was recently published as *open access* in *Solar Physics* (*Sol Phys* 299, 133 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11207-024-02378-9>).

For the upcoming *European Space Weather Week (ESWW)* 04-08 November 2024 (<https://esww2024.org/>) several presentations on SPEARHEAD's ongoing efforts have been submitted and will be presented. On top of that, as declared in the DoA, the project will also be presented during the Space Weather fair. Finally, a business meeting has been booked, since ESWW is an excellent opportunity for the Partners of the project to discuss the progress and the next steps. In addition, SPEARHEAD joined the EU Booster (<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>) Cluster on Space Weather in which other EU projects such as SWATNet (Space Weather Awareness Training Network; <https://swatnet.eu/>), SOLER (Energetic Solar Eruptions: Data and Analysis Tools; <https://soler-horizon.eu/>), and SERPENTINE (Solar energetic particle analysis platform for the inner heliosphere; <https://serpentine-h2020.eu/>) are also members. To this end, the requested booth at ESWW will be supported by the Booster and thus will be inclusive of the other EU projects - enhancing the collaboration and finally impact between current efforts. Additionally, the business meeting will be a shared one with the SOLER EU project (<https://soler-horizon.eu/>) increasing the osmosis between projects creating communication and facilitating collaboration.

As noted in Task 8-4, communication activities (*Figure 3-2*) encompassed media interviews (including newspapers and public journal articles), a television appearance, a public outreach presentation, and discussion sessions with schools. Additionally, the *News* section of the **SPEARHEAD** portal regularly provided updated information on the project's progress and outcomes, which were subsequently disseminated through **SPEARHEAD's** social media channels.

Figure 3-2 - Composite figure with instances of the project's dissemination and communication activities

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List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AMS	Alpha Magnetic Spectrometer
AU	Astronomical Units
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research
CDF	Common Data Format
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DASH	Data Analysis and Software in Heliophysics
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECRS	European Cosmic Ray Symposium
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
ESA	European Space Agency
ESAC	European Space Astronomy Center
ESWW	European Space Weather Week
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FD	Forbush Decrease

GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
GME	Goddard Medium Energy
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
HEPAD	High Energy Proton and Alpha Detector
HET	High Energy Telescope
ICME	Interplanetary CME
IMP	Interplanetary Monitoring Platform
ISTP	International Solar-Terrestrial Physics
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NM	Neutron Monitor
PAMELA	Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics
PI	Principal Investigator
RANSAC	Random sample consensus
SDO	Solar Dynamics Observatory
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SHINE	Solar Heliospheric and INterplanetary Environment
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
Solo	Solar Orbiter

SPEARHEAD	SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SXR	Soft X-ray
SREM	Standard Radiation Environment Monitor
YF	Yield Function